

ENHANCING FRONT-END EFFICIENCY WITH SERVER-SIDE RENDERING TECHNIQUES IN HIGH TRAFFIC ENVIRONMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908737>

Abstract

This paper analyzes frontend performance optimization using server-side rendering (SSR) techniques under high load conditions. The basic principles of SSR, its impact and associated complexities such as increased server load and development complexity are examined. Key techniques for improving SSR performance such as caching, code splitting, and incremental static generation are explored.

Keywords: server-side rendering (SSR), client-side rendering (CSR), frontend optimization, high-load systems, web application performance, web application scaling, search engine optimization (SEO), caching.

Introduction

In contemporary web development, the demand for quick, interactive, and dynamic user interfaces has reached unprecedented levels. The shift towards single-page applications (SPA), which rely heavily on client-side rendering (CSR), has introduced new challenges related to performance and scalability, especially under high load. While CSR provides high interactivity by executing JavaScript on the client side, it can also result in slower initial page load times, particularly on devices with limited computational resources or in environments with poor network conditions.

Server-Side Rendering (SSR) has gained prominence as a viable solution for optimizing frontend performance. It pre-renders the HTML on the server, delivering fully-rendered content to the client before JavaScript takes over to manage interactions. This method significantly reduces the time to first contentful paint (FCP) and improves user experience in scenarios with high load or poor connectivity, making it particularly useful for high-traffic applications. The aim of this

study – to analyze different methods for improving frontend efficiency using server rendering under high load conditions.

Main part. Core principles of SSR and its impact on frontend performance

The method of SSR has emerged as an important technique for enhancing the performance of web applications, particularly under high load conditions [1]. Its core purpose is to reduce page load times, improve responsiveness, and decrease the computational burden on client devices. Unlike CSR, which relies on the client to build and display the page, SSR involves the server generating and delivering fully rendered HTML pages. SSR enhances user experience by improving page load times and interactivity, which can positively affect user engagement and retention, particularly in e-commerce and financial applications [2]. Recent studies show that SSR is a faster rendering method than CSR, achieving higher performance metrics at all stages (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Speed and time performance results of SCR and SSR [3]

Designed to offload rendering tasks from the client to the server, SSR delivers pre-rendered content to users. This is particularly beneficial in high-load environments where reducing the strain on client devices and accelerating the time to FCP is crucial. The SSR process involves several stages. Initially, the client submits a request to the server. Upon receiving the request, the server retrieves the necessary data, typically from an external API or a database, and proceeds to generate the corresponding HTML content. The fully rendered

HTML document is then transmitted back to the client, allowing the content to be displayed immediately upon receipt. Subsequently, additional resources such as CSS and JavaScript files are fetched asynchronously [4]. This asynchronous loading ensures that user interaction becomes available after the initial content is displayed, enhancing the overall responsiveness of the application. While SSR offers significant improvements in performance and user experience, it also introduces complexities that must be considered.

Table 1.

Advantages and disadvantages of using the SSR method		
Advantages	Disadvantages	Potential solutions
Faster initial page load due to pre-rendered HTML sent from the server.	Increased server load, as the server needs to render every page request.	The use of caching strategies to reduce server load.
Improved SEO because search engines can index pre-rendered content.	More complex development process, as SSR requires a balance between server and client logic.	The adoption of frameworks that simplify SSR and offer integrated client-side solutions (e.g., Next.js).
Better accessibility, especially for users with slow internet connections or older devices.	Potential latency issues due to the need for server-side data fetching and HTML generation.	Optimization of server response times by pre-fetching critical data or using edge servers.
Enhanced performance on mobile devices by reducing the need for heavy JavaScript execution.	Scaling SSR in high-traffic environments requires additional infrastructure, such as load balancing and caching.	The leverage of Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) and horizontal scaling for high-traffic environments.
Supports rich, dynamic content while maintaining fast rendering times.	Maintenance of both server-side and client-side code, increasing development overhead.	The use of hybrid rendering approaches that combine SSR and CSR to balance performance.

The choice of SSR method directly influences the performance of the frontend, particularly in terms of load times, interactivity, and scalability. It is important to examine the key performance metrics affected by SSR and how different methods may optimize these metrics under high-load conditions.

Time to FCP measures how quickly meaningful content is displayed on the user's screen. The method of SSR, by pre-rendering HTML on the server, generally improves FCP by eliminating the need for the client to download and execute JavaScript before rendering content. Full SSR tends to offer the best FCP improvements, but hybrid and edge rendering approaches can also provide fast FCP under certain conditions. **Time to interactive (TTI)** measures how quickly a page becomes fully interactive. While SSR helps improve FCP, the page may still require additional assets (such as JavaScript) to become fully interactive.

Methods such as SSR provide a significant boost to **search engine optimization (SEO)** by delivering pre-rendered HTML, that search engines can index more easily. In contrast, CSR applications often struggle with SEO, as they require JavaScript execution before content is visible. All SSR methods improve SEO, but full SSR and edge rendering are particularly effective in ensuring that search engine crawlers can access and index content rapidly.

Understanding the core principles of SSR is critical for optimizing frontend performance, since it offers significant benefits, such as faster initial page loads and improved SEO. However, it also introduces complexities that require careful management, including increased server load and more intricate development processes. Moreover, ensuring robust security measures in SSR environments is just as crucial as in automotive systems, especially in high-traffic applications where the risk of data breaches increases [5]. By balancing these factors, SSR can significantly enhance the performance and scalability of modern web applications.

Optimization SSR strategies and methods for high-load applications

A method of SSR offers numerous benefits for web applications, including faster initial load times, improved SEO, and better performance on mobile devices. However, these advantages come with a cost: the server bears a significant portion of the load, especially when handling a high volume of user requests. As the number of users accessing the application increases, the performance and scalability of SSR-based applications can suffer.

Caching is one of the most effective techniques to optimize SSR in high-load environments. By storing pre-rendered HTML pages or fragments, caching reduces the server's need to regenerate content for each request, significantly improving response times and reducing CPU load.

In many scenarios, static or semi-static pages do not change frequently, making them ideal candidates for **full-page caching**. By caching the entire HTML output, subsequent requests can be served directly from the cache, bypassing the SSR process. Solutions like Varnish, NGINX, or Redis are commonly used for caching full pages.

For dynamic applications where only parts of the page change, **fragment caching** is an excellent strategy. With this approach, static portions of the page (e.g., headers or footers) are cached, while dynamic content is rendered as needed. Fragment caching allows for faster content updates while maintaining high performance.

Tools such as Cloudflare or Akamai help offload traffic from the main server by caching pre-rendered HTML pages and serving them from edge servers. By placing content closer to the end-user, **edge caching** reduces latency and increases response times. This strategy is particularly useful for global applications where users are distributed across different geographic regions.

Code splitting and **lazy loading** help optimize the delivery of JavaScript files, ensuring that the client only receives the necessary code for the current page. These techniques improve the TTI metric by reducing the amount of JavaScript that needs to be parsed and executed on the client side. By breaking up large JavaScript bundles into smaller, more manageable chunks, code splitting reduces the amount of data the browser needs to download initially. Modern SSR frameworks like Next.js and Nuxt.js offer automatic code splitting by default, loading only the essential JavaScript for the current page and deferring non-critical parts until they are needed.

Lazy loading further optimizes page performance by loading non-essential assets (such as images or additional JavaScript) only when they are required. For instance, lazy loading can defer the loading of below-the-fold content until the user scrolls down to view it, reducing the initial page load time. Lazy loading images and videos can also save bandwidth, which is especially beneficial for users on slow networks.

To handle high traffic and prevent server overload, **load balancing** is an essential strategy for optimizing SSR applications. Load balancers distribute incoming requests evenly across multiple servers, ensuring that no single server becomes overwhelmed. With horizontal scaling, additional server instances are added to handle increased traffic. Load balancers such as NGINX, HAProxy, or cloud-based solutions like AWS Elastic Load Balancer distribute traffic across these instances, improving both performance and resilience. Horizontal scaling also enables high availability by allowing applications to remain operational even if one or more servers fail.

In cases where user sessions are required (e.g., authentication), sticky sessions ensure that requests from the same user are consistently routed to the same server. This minimizes the overhead of having to reprocess session data on different servers, improving response times for logged-in users.

Incremental Static Regeneration (ISR) is a powerful technique that combines the benefits of static site generation (SSG) with SSR. It allows static pages to be regenerated on-demand while the application continues to serve cached versions of the page. Studies show, that SSG rendering method is one of the fastest models with a completion time of 1839 ms [6]. This approach provides real-time content updates without the need for full-page re-rendering. In ISR, developers set specific time intervals during which pages are revalidated and regenerated. Frameworks like Next.js natively support ISR, enabling developers to dynamically regenerate static content while minimizing server load. For applications that need real-time updates, ISR also supports manual triggers for revalidation. When content is updated (e.g., a new blog post is published), the server can regenerate the relevant page immediately, ensuring users always see the latest information.

In high-load environments, it is critical to optimize how data is fetched and delivered to the client. **Asynchronous data fetching** reduces latency and allows the server to process multiple requests simultaneously without blocking the main thread. With concurrent data

fetching, multiple API calls are made simultaneously, reducing the overall time required to gather data. This is especially useful in complex SSR applications where multiple data sources need to be queried. Techniques like 'Promise.all()' in JavaScript or async/await patterns help ensure that data fetching is performed as efficiently as possible.

Reducing the size of assets transferred between the server and the client is another key optimization strategy for SSR applications. **Compression and minification** help minimize the load on the network and accelerate the delivery of resources. Both Gzip and Brotli are widely used compression algorithms that significantly reduce the size of HTML, CSS, and JavaScript files. By compressing assets before they are sent to the client, server response times are reduced, improving the overall performance of the application.

Optimizing SSR in high-load environments is essential for maintaining application performance, reducing server strain, and ensuring scalability. Caching, load balancing, and code splitting are foundational strategies that reduce server overhead, while advanced techniques like ISR further improve efficiency. Recently, with the development of artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies, which are widely used in various industries, it can become possible to enhance SSR performance [7]. As the demand for fast, responsive web applications continues to grow, employing these optimization strategies allows developers to deliver a superior user experience without sacrificing performance under heavy traffic [8].

Conclusion

In high-traffic environments, maintaining front-end performance is critical to delivering a seamless user experience. A method SSR has emerged as an effective technique for optimizing front-end efficiency by addressing key challenges such as initial page load times, SEO, and scalability. By pre-rendering content on the server and delivering it directly to the client, SSR reduces the computational burden on the client-side and enhances the perceived performance of web applications. As modern web applications continue to grow in complexity and traffic demands, adopting and refining SSR methods will remain critical to ensuring that web applications perform efficiently and deliver high-quality user experiences across a broad range of devices and network conditions.

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